

EFFECT OF THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS STITCHING AND FIBRE ARCHITECTURE ON THE INTERLAMINAR PROPERTIES OF FLAX/EPOXY LAMINATES

M. Ravandi^{1, 2,a}, W. S. Teo^{2,b}, L. Q. N. Tran^{2,c}, M. S. Yong^{1, 2,d} and T. E. Tay^{1,e}

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Singapore
9 Engineering Drive 1, 117575, Singapore
Web page: <http://me.nus.edu.sg>

²Forming Technology Group, Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology
71 Nanyang Drive, 638075, Singapore
Web page: <http://www.simtech.a-star.edu.sg>

^a m.ravandi@u.nus.edu , ^b wsteo@simtech.a-star.edu.sg , ^c tranlqn@simtech.a-star.edu.sg ,
^d msyong@simtech.a-star.edu.sg , ^e mpetayte@nus.edu.sg

Keywords: Flax fibres, Laminated natural fibre composites, Stitching, Mode I delamination, DCB

ABSTRACT

The delamination resistance of continuous long flax fibre laminates were evaluated and the effects of through-the-thickness stitching using natural fibres on the in-plane tensile properties as well as interlaminar fracture toughness were experimentally studied. Twist-less flax yarn and cotton thread were used to stitch the preforms and various stitch densities were prepared, and then processed by Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI). Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test were conducted to measure Mode I critical strain energy release rate (G_{IC}). Knowing that cross-section area of flax yarn is much greater than cotton thread, it is observed that the reduction in tensile properties that caused by stitching process is almost the same for both stitch material and can reach up to 20% in the highest stitch density. In terms of delamination improvement, it was found that cotton thread stitch does not necessarily improve interlaminar toughness, whereas stitching with flax yarn improved it at least 10% (at very low stitch density) compared to unstitched composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the use of man-made fibre reinforced polymer composites has grown intensively due to their potential to combine high mechanical properties with low weight and become preferred materials for various applications such as automotive, aerospace, marine and construction. Although these materials have desirable properties for most of aforementioned applications, their use are restricted because of increasing demand for eco-friendly materials from renewable resources. In this regard, it is found that plant fibres can be the most appropriate alternative of synthetic fibres in many applications. Among the different types of available plant fibres, flax fibres are one of the more interesting reinforcing fibres for composite industry in terms of physical and mechanical properties. Higher specific strength and stiffness, good vibration damping and acoustic behavior as well as their lower environmental impact and costs of flax fibres offer highest reinforcing potential in composite materials in order to replace man-made glass fibres not only in nonstructural products but also in higher performance applications.

Natural fibres in the form of short fibres or non-woven mats are very common and widely used in composite industry for producing nonstructural components. But in order to replace glass fibres in load-

bearing applications and use the maximum performance and load carrying capacity of natural fibres, it is necessary to utilize fibres in continuous aligned form such as unidirectional (UD) or fabric using optimum twisted yarn in manufacturing composites [1]. For example, Bensadoun et al. [2] have compared the impact resistance and fatigue behavior of continuous flax fibre composites with various preform architectures. Their experimental results showed that overly UD flax fibre with epoxy resin had better tensile performance in static loading, whereas the plain woven flax composite showed better fatigue behavior. Similarly, the effect of lay-up stacking sequence and number of preform layers on the tensile and compressive properties of plain woven flax fabric/epoxy composite was studied by Muralidhar [3]. As expected, fibre volume fraction found the main parameter governing the tensile properties, while the increase in the number of plies deteriorates the tensile strength. In such natural fibre laminates similar to conventional fibre laminates, interlaminar failure or delamination is one of the most important failure mode which rarely reported for these composites so far. Therefore, characterization the interlaminar fracture toughness and understanding the fracture mechanism of natural fibre laminates with various fibre architectures are crucial in order to design and predict failure. Liu et al. [4] assessed influences of some parameters such as yarn linear density, weave configuration and stacking sequence on the intralaminar fracture toughness of the commercially woven flax textile laminates using compact tension test. It was found that higher fibre volume fraction improves the fracture toughness of composites while textile architecture has notable effect on the tensile modulus and strength. Rong et al. [5] characterized mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of stitched and unstitched unidirectional sisal/epoxy laminates by means of Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test and studied the factors that influence in-plane mechanical responses. In the other study, carbon nanotube buckypaper interleaf has been utilized in between unidirectional flax fibre layers in order to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of laminate [6].

The purpose of this work is to study the effect of preform architecture and through-the-thickness stitching density on the static behavior of flax fibre composites impregnated by epoxy matrix using resin infusion technique. Accordingly, the mechanical properties including tensile strength and stiffness, and interlaminar fracture toughness are characterized experimentally for various stitch densities using two different materials as well as various preform architectures.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

A low-viscosity thermo-set resin system Epolam 5051 (mixed viscosity: 200 mPa.s at 25°C) was used as polymer matrix. Woven 4×4 hopsack standard fabric using 250tex twist-less flax yarn supplied by Composite Evolution Co. and UD flax fibres supplied by Lineo were used as reinforcement. Moreover, 30tex Cotton thread from Gütermann Co. and 250tex twist-less flax yarn, the yarn used to weave the flax fabric, were utilized for stitching purposes.

2.2 Preform Architecture

In order to stitch the preforms, cotton thread and flax yarn have been used. Cotton thread stitching were conducted using commercial sewing machine, whereas flax yarn stitching were performed by hand using the similar stitching pattern. Fig. 1 shows the micrograph of stitched plain weave flax fabric laminate by cotton thread and flax yarn. For DCB test specimens' preparation, a region of the preforms was left unstitched to accommodate a nonadhesive film (PTFE) insert that acts as a pre-crack. For tensile test specimens, entire preforms were stitched uniformly. In order to have a clear observation of Stitch Density (SD) influences on the fracture toughness as well as the mechanical properties of flax fibre laminates, from each stitch material (cotton thread and flax yarn) four different stitch densities were produced. To quantify these stitch densities, and also to make easier comparison between them, the dimensionless formula was defined as follow:

$$Stitch\ Density = \frac{1}{S_L \times S_R} \Big|_{Stitch\ in\ warp\ direction} + \frac{1}{S_L \times S_R} \Big|_{Stitch\ in\ weft\ direction} \quad (1)$$

where S_L and S_R are distance between two adjacent stitches in the same line and spacing between two adjacent stitch lines, respectively. Table 1 illustrates the detail information of all preforms used in this study.

Figure 1. Micrograph of the through-the-thickness stitch: a) cotton thread stitch; b) flax yarn stitch

Flax Lamina preform	Density (g/m ²)	Layup	Stitch material	Stitch Density		Supplier
				Quantitative	Qualitative	
4×4 Plain Weave	500	[0] ₄	Unstitched	0	Unstitched	Composite Evolution
		[0] ₄	Cotton	0.04	Very low	
		[0] ₄	Cotton	0.08	low	
		[0] ₄	Cotton	0.98	high	
		[0] ₄	Cotton	0.17	Very high	
		[0] ₄	Flax	0.01	Very low	
		[0] ₄	Flax	0.015	low	
		[0] ₄	Flax	0.02	high	
		[0] ₄	Flax	0.03	Very high	
UD	110	[0] ₁₆	Unstitched	0	Unstitched	Lineo

Table 1: Characteristics and stitch parameters of fabricated flax fibre laminates

2.3 Composite Manufacturing

Polymer matrix composites with man-made fibre reinforcements are proceed and manufactured by numerous methods such as hand lay-up, prepeg, liquid compression molding, pultrusion, filament winding, autoclave processing and liquid composite molding (e.g. RTM, vacuum infusion and resin infusion) techniques. Majority of these manufacturing methods can be utilized in order to process flax fibre composites where the process temperature less than 170°C. Among these methods, liquid composite molding techniques are the most widely used and often reported as the main manufacturing technique for thermoset natural fibre composites because of their many advantages such as cost-effective, potential of automation, short processing cycle, high final production quality, etc. Nevertheless, impregnation of natural fibres is different than synthetic fibres because of special structure of natural fibres that causes less permeability to resin flow. Moreover, because of lower permeability of single fibres in comparison to entire preforms, and hollow structure (lumen) of fibres, often voids are created in the laminate as the resin penetrates inside single fibres. So, the injection speed and viscosity of the resin must be controlled during composite processing to have optimum impregnation.

In this study, the preforms were processed by Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) technique at

room temperature. The prepared preform which covered by release plies at top and bottom faces was sealed by vacuum bag and evacuated for 2 hrs to remove the air inside the mold. The mixture of resin and hardener after degassing for 30 min in vacuum chamber, was infused to the mold through the resin inlet tube till the entire preform was wetted, then then inlet valve was closed. The temperature was then increased to 65°C for 2 hrs to be de-molded and post cured at 80°C for 16 hrs.

The fibre volume fraction of prepared panels were measured after processing the composites. For this purpose, gas pycnometer was used to measure the densities of pure cured matrix, dry fibre and composite where the samples were drawn from different parts of panels. Knowing the weight and density of fiber, matrix and composite, corresponding fibre volume fraction was calculated. Assuming no void content, an average fibre volume fraction of 30% was obtained for the woven fabric and 39% for the unidirectional fibre composites.

2.4 Micrograph and Scanning Electron Microscopy

With the purpose of assessing initial defects such as voids, unimpregnated areas, and the quality of impregnation, optical and scanning electron microscopy were performed on the randomly selected parts of prepared panels. This study helps to have more accurate interpretation of fracture mechanism in the tested samples.

Fig.2a shows optical microscopic image of an arbitrary section of plain weave flax laminate where weft and warp fibres are mentioned. In this scale, there is no visible impregnation defect or void inside the panel. Most of the time, extracting all single fibres in fibre hackling process is impossible and flax fibres remain in the form of technical fibre bundle [7]. Due to very low permeability of these bundle against the resin, usually un-impregnated zone can be found inside these bundles. In Fig. 2b cross section of these fibre bundle and their impregnation are shown. As it can be seen, resin penetrated inside fibre bundles and no defect is observed. The SEM image of a fibre bundle shown in Fig. 2c also proves the good impregnation of fibre bundle and no significant defect is detectable. It has to be noted that the dark scratches on the optical microscopic images are related to quality of specimen polishing and preparation.

Figure 2. a) Optical microscopy of 4x4 plain woven flax/epoxy composite; b) optical microcopy of a fibre bundle in the same composite; c) SEM of a fractured fibre bundle in the same composite.

2.5 Composite Tensile test

Tensile and flexural tests were carried out using a Shimadzu universal tensile test machine at room temperature, 65% relative humidity, with a load cell of 50 kN. The test specimens for each sample were cut from the same panel with an average thickness of 4 mm and dimensions of 250x25 mm according to ASTM D3039. Based on ASTM standard recommendation, the specimens were tested at a crosshead displacement speed of 2 mm/min and at least five specimens were tested to attain repeatable results with reliable standard deviations.

2.6 Double cantilever beam test

Mode I delamination tests were performed on the prepared specimens using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test method. The schematic of DCB test Specimen and the dimensions are shown in Fig. 3a. In order to prevent large deformation and failure of specimen's arms, 2 mm thickness unidirectional CFRP tabs were bonded to both sides of DCB specimens. Also, aluminum load blocks were bound to both arms of specimens to transfer opening forces. The tests were conducted on an INSTRON 4505 universal testing machine with loading rate of 1 mm/min and 1 kN load cell. The prepared specimens were tested according to ASTM D5528 standard and the modified beam theory (MBT) were used to calculate mode I critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} . Fig. 3b shows the DCB test specimen mounted on an Instron 4505 universal testing machine which was conducted at SIMTech mechanics Lab.

Figure 3: a) Schematic of Tabbed double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen configuration; b) Mounted Tabbed DCB test specimen on the testing machine

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of stitching on the tensile properties of plain woven flax composite

The average tensile properties of unstitched and stitched laminated composites using cotton thread and flax yarn with various stitch densities are illustrated in Fig. 4. In order to be able to compare effects of stitch densities of both stitch materials together, despite the difference in quantitative values, only the qualitative values of stitch densities according to Table 1 are considered to plot results.

As it can be seen, regardless of the stitch material's type, both tensile strength and modulus decline by increasing stitch density. This behavior of stitched flax fibre composite is very similar to those of reported for stitched conventional fibre composites [8-9]. According to our results, cotton thread stitch declines tensile properties up to 15%, and the deterioration by flax yarn stitch can reach to 20% in tensile strength and 15% in tensile modulus in very high stitch densities. It is worthwhile to note that stitching process, depending on stitch density and thread size, generally causes damages to the laminates because of cutting or crimping the reinforcing fibres which leads to stress concentration around stitch points. Consequently, stitched laminates are normally weaker than unstitched ones in terms of in-plane tensile properties [5]. Although the cross-section area of flax yarn is almost ten times greater than that of cotton thread, the reduction in tensile properties is not so different. This may be due to particular texture of the utilized textile for preform.

We used the 4x4 hopsack woven flax fabric as the enforcing textile wherein an empty space exists between its warp and weft fibres. We deliberately chose the stitch length in a way that we used these spaces to locate the stitches to minimize the damages induced to preform fibres. So, regardless of stitch yarn diameter, minimum fibres were damaged by needle during stitching process. Therefore, the prominent reason to reduction in tensile properties due to stitching is because of crimping the reinforcing

fibres and the resin pockets that created around the stitch points. Moreover, due to the size of these empty spaces which is as big as a flax yarn, the dimension of stitch thread does not have significant effect on the tensile properties.

Figure 4: Effects of various stitch densities on the tensile strength and modulus of woven flax fibre composite. (a) Tensile strength against increasing stitch density; (b) Tensile modulus against increasing stitch density

3.1 Effects of stitching on the interlaminar fracture toughness

The average values of the Mode I interlaminar (delamination) fracture toughness (G_{IC}) of the stitched and unstitched woven flax laminates using cotton thread and flax yarn as well as unstitched unidirectional (UD) flax fibres and man-made glass fibres are shown in Fig. 5. The values of G_{IC} were calculated using modified beam theory and its average values from crack propagation were considered. These information is useful in understanding the effects of stitch density parameter to fulfill the design requirements of interlaminar toughness. We found that in a similar condition (same resin and manufacturing process), UD flax laminate shows almost two times higher delamination resistance than UD man-made glass fibre composite. This superiority is even more significant (almost five times) for woven flax laminates in comparison with interlaminar toughness of other conventional composites [10]. This is mainly due to high degree of fibre bridging in the crack tip region in the natural fibre laminate [5]. Although the flax fibre bundles are aligned in certain direction, they are not as uniform as conventional fibre and the single fibres have irregular orientations. During the lay-up, this characteristic of flax fibres result intensive nesting in-between the planes and consequently high fibre bridging in delamination process. Furthermore, the fracture surface study of delaminated flax fibre laminates revealed that unlike the delamination of conventional composites, fibre pull out and fracture are the dominant failure mechanism. In other words, fibre breakage makes up a great contribution in the energy absorption (G_{IC}) during crack propagation.

Figure 5: Effects of various stitch densities and fibre architecture on the interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC})

Also, it is observed from Fig. 5 that through-the-thickness stitching with cotton thread does not necessarily improve interlaminar fracture toughness. According to experimental observation, only highest density of cotton stitch improved G_{IC} while lower densities deteriorate it. In fact, due to low strength of cotton thread, the amount of G_{IC} improvement by adding through-the-thickness

reinforcements, is not more than the deterioration of interlaminar toughness because of fibre damage caused by the stitching process. In other words, the wrecking effects of resin pockets and voids (which are induced by stitching process around the stitch threads or yarns), are greater than the beneficial effects of cotton-thread stitch bridging on the delamination resistance. On the other hand, unlike the cotton stitch laminates, and regardless of stitch density, the delamination resistance of flax stitched composites was improved at least 10% compared to unstitched composite. It is worth noting that although the linear density and cross-section area of flax yarn are higher than that of cotton thread, its quantitative stitch density is lower (Table 1). From comparing the improvements in interlaminar toughness against reduction in tensile properties, it can be concluded that the performance of twist-less flax yarn stitch is higher than cotton thread stitch.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Goutianos, T. Peijs, B. Nystrom, and M. Skrifvars, "Development of Flax Fibre based Textile Reinforcements for Composite Applications," *Appl. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 199–215, Jul. 2006.
- [2] F. Bensadoun, D. Depuydt, J. Baets, V. Vuure, A. Willem, and I. Verpoest, "Influence of fibre architecture on impact and fatigue behaviour of flax fibre-based composites," in *The 19th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM19), Montreal, Canada; 2013*, 2013.
- [3] B. A. Muralidhar, "Tensile and compressive properties of flax-plain weave preform reinforced epoxy composites," *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 207–213, Feb. 2013.
- [4] Q. Liu and M. Hughes, "The fracture behaviour and toughness of woven flax fibre reinforced epoxy composites," *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 1644–1652, Oct. 2008.
- [5] M. Z. Rong, M. Q. Zhang, Y. Liu, Z. W. Zhang, G. C. Yang, and H. M. Zeng, "Effect of Stitching on In-Plane and Interlaminar Properties of Sisal/Epoxy Laminates," *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 1505–1526, Jun. 2002.
- [6] C. Chen, Y. Li, and T. Yu, "Interlaminar toughening in flax fiber-reinforced composites interleaved with carbon nanotube buckypaper," *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 33, no. 20, pp. 1859–1868, Oct. 2014.
- [7] O. Faruk and M. Sain, *Biofiber Reinforcements in Composite Materials*. Elsevier, 2014.
- [8] K. Dransfield, C. Baillie, and Y.-W. Mai, "Improving the delamination resistance of CFRP by stitching—a review," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 305–317, 1994.
- [9] H. Heß and N. Himmel, "Structurally stitched NCF CFRP laminates. Part 2: Finite element unit cell based prediction of in-plane strength," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 569–585, Mar. 2011.
- [10] K. A. Dransfield, L. K. Jain, and Y.-W. Mai, "On the effects of stitching in CFRPs—I. mode I delamination toughness," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 815–827, 1998.